

EVALUATION AND MANAGEMENT OF ECOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL RISKS IN BANKS THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. The article describes the development of artificial intelligence and the introduction and development of artificial intelligence in economic sectors. Also, the prospects of automation of the sector in banks and the use of artificial intelligence in the assessment and management of environmental and social risks are presented.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, automation, banking, environmental and social risks, risk assessment and management, model.*

Annotatsiya. Maqolada bugungi kunda sun'iy intellektning rivojlanib borishi va iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarida sun'iy intellektning kirib kelishi va rivojlanish jarayonlari keltirib o'tilgan. Shuningdek, banklarda sohani avtomatlashtirish istiqbollari hamda ekologik va ijtimoiy risklarni baholash va boshqarishda sun'iy intellektning qo'llanilishi keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *sun'iy intellekt, avtomatlashtirish, bank, ekologik va ijtimoiy risklar, risklarni baholash va boshqarish, model.*

Аннотация. В статье рассказывается о развитии искусственного интеллекта сегодня, а также о процессах внедрения и развития искусственного интеллекта в отраслях экономики. В нем также представлены перспективы автоматизации отрасли в банках и применения искусственного интеллекта для оценки и управления экологическими и социальными рисками.

Ключевые слова: *искусственный интеллект, автоматизация, банковское дело, экологические и социальные риски, оценка рисков и управление ими, модель.*

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (English: artificial intelligence, AI) is a field of science and technology aimed at creating machines capable of imitating human intelligence. Artificial intelligence began to appear in the middle of the last century, with the development of computer technology. The Turing Test by Alan Turing [1] in the 1950s was proposed, which became an important basis for evaluating the ability of computers to replicate human intelligence.

In the early years, artificial intelligence relied mainly on rule-based systems and simple algorithms. In the 1980s, artificial intelligence began to evolve further with the development of artificial neural networks and machine learning technologies. Since the 2000s, big data and powerful computing power have taken artificial intelligence to a new level. Today, artificial intelligence is widely used in various fields, including medicine, finance, transportation, and everyday life.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The answer to the question of what artificial intelligence itself is as follows: artificial intelligence is considered a separate field of Informatics, which is usually concerned with the creation of a computer system of joint capabilities with the human mind. Including the creation of systems such as language comprehension, discussion, translation and computation [2].

By now, artificial intelligence consists of algorithms designed to perform various actions, and it is capable of doing a few things that the human mind can do. An example of this is the first copywriter in history, who defeated the 1997 IBM computer chess world champion Garry Kasparov named Deep Blue. It is also necessary to point out about the IBM Watson supercomputer, this technology was able to answer questions asked in a specific language based on its base [3].

According to a number of foreign researchers, artificial intelligence is the driver of the digital transformation process, providing all participants in economic processes with the transition to a new stage of machine cooperation with a person, and in turn, leading to the further development of digital platforms and the digital economy in the future [4].

Today, we can highlight several important benefits of using artificial intelligence (AI) in banks. Their main ones are:

1. Data analysis. In this - AI enables the rapid processing and analysis of large data. This helps banks gain a deeper understanding of their customers.

2. Risk management. With the help of artificial intelligence, banks can make more accurate forecasts when assessing credit risk. This, in turn, improves the lending process and is important in risk management.

3. Fraud detection. SI algorithms help detect unusual behavior, which can reduce fraud and increase financial security.

4. Customer Service. With the help of chatbots and virtual assistants, customer service can be provided 24/7. This allows us to provide quick and efficient responses to customers regarding services.

5. Personalization. With the help of AI, banks can offer services and products tailored to the needs of customers, which will further enhance customer relationships.

6. Operational efficiency: Artificial intelligence can help automate processes, which can reduce costs and increase operational efficiency.

7. Forecasting. AI enables banks to predict market trends and customer behavior, which is useful in making strategic decisions.

8. Support for employees. Artificial intelligence can help employees with complex tasks, such as analyzing data or advising customers. This will increase productivity.

9. Financial advice. With AI, banks can offer personalized advice to help customers with financial planning. These services help clients achieve their financial goals.

10. Analytical reports. Artificial intelligence can automatically prepare analytical reports and assist bank management in making decisions.

11. Market competition. With the help of AI, banks will be able to develop competitive strategies and quickly adapt to market changes.

12. Preventing problems. With the help of AI, potential problems can be identified in advance and measures can be taken in time, which makes the bank's operation more stable.

Artificial intelligence sums up recommendations for the most powerful portfolios, depending on the specific investor's short-and long-term goals. In addition, it provides the information necessary for credit professionals to make decisions based on them [5].

Along with the above, when it comes to environmental and social risks in banking activities, banks use different models and approaches to manage and reduce these risks.

I. Climate and social risks in banks:

Climate and social risks are a serious concern for the banking sector as these risks can affect their financial stability, reputation and compliance.

- Environmental climate risks -physical risks, including natural disasters, extreme weather events and long-term climate change, and transition risks (technology or market dynamics);

- Social risks -these risks relate to the impact of social issues such as human rights violations, labor practices, inequality, and reputational damage due to a company's or bank's involvement in socially harmful activities.

II. Artificial intelligence models in climate and social risk management.

a) Risk assessment models.

1. Climate risk models

Important components, data warehouses, and algorithms are needed to better understand climate risk models in banking and how artificial intelligence can be used to create these models.

Climate risk models are used by banks to estimate and predict the financial impact of climate-related events or transitions, such as extreme weather (hurricanes, floods, fires), regulatory changes and market change (demand), green technologies).

The process of using AI to build climate risk models involves the following steps:

1) Data collection and processing. Any AI model, including climate risk models, requires high-quality and diverse datasets.

2) Choosing the right and appropriate algorithms. After the data is collected and processed, the next step is to select the appropriate AI algorithms. There are various machine learning and AI techniques that can be applied to climate risk modeling.

3) Model training and testing. After the algorithms are selected, the next step is to train the model using the available data.

4) Model evaluation. Model evaluation is necessary to ensure that it accurately predicts risks. Banks can model different climate scenarios (for example, a 2°C or 4°C temperature rise) and conduct scenario analysis to understand how each scenario would affect financial performance.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays an important role in optimizing investment portfolios by incorporating ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) factors. In this process, two main models include:

1. ESG Scoring Models

ESG Scoring Models at AI assesses companies for compliance with environmental, social and governance criteria. These models help banks to determine the sustainability of their investments.

ESG Scoring Models Using the By doing this, it helps to reduce risks in making investment decisions.

2. Sustainable Investment Models

AI-based algorithms ensure portfolios are optimized to balance returns with low climate and social risks. These models assess the long-term sustainability of investments in sectors affected by climate change or social trends.

Key benefits of incorporating ESG factors using AI:

Data analysis: AI algorithms support investment decisions by quickly analyzing large amounts of data;

decision making: Considering ESG scores, investors can create strategies aimed at minimizing risks and increasing sustainability;

Monitoring and updating: AI-based systems can continuously monitor changes in market conditions and ESG scores, allowing for portfolio updates over time.

In short, by optimizing ESG factors, AI enables banks and other financial institutions to create sustainable investment strategies that allow them to maintain a balance between financial goals and social responsibility.

The application of these models helps align financial goals with sustainability goals, allowing investors to identify investment opportunities that have a positive impact on the environment.

Through the use of artificial intelligence capabilities, service enterprises can simplify operations, improve efficiency, improve asset utilization and overall performance, optimize costs.

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